

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS ON OPEN-HOLE CARBON-FIBRE/EPOXY STITCHED LAMINATES WITH DIFFERENT STITCH ORIENTATION

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Keywords: Open-hole stitch composite, Open-hole tension, Stress concentration factor

ABSTRACT

Open-hole carbon-fibre/epoxy (T300/EP3631) laminates with stitch thread of Kevlar-29 have been analyzed for deformation behavior on tensile loading. Stitch around the notch are oriented on longitudinal and transverse direction having stitch pitch of 3mm and stitch spacing of 12mm. Numerical analysis at macroscopic structural level for the result validation, in-plane characteristics and their origin mechanism stitched laminates is the kernel in this research. Woven laminate structures with twenty layers of [0/90]₂₀, hole diameter 6.35mm and thickness 4.2mm, following ASTM standard D5766 instructions have been modeled and analyzed with finite element method, using commercially available software; MSC Patran/ Nastran. In order to obtain macroscopic and local stress-strain distribution, open-hole laminates have been modelled on ply-by-ply basis. The laminates and stitch threads are individually modeled with 8 node solid elements. A lamina which consists of woven textile and matrix resin has been modeled as homogeneous orthotropic material. Single element per lamina through thickness of laminate has been generated. While, interfaces between matrix and stitch yarns are assumed to be perfectly glued and modelled by contact capability in the solver. Furthermore, node-to-surface algorithm of contact detection had been adopted to represent contact on deformable body. The finite element result showed an analogous pattern of stress-strain distribution on longitudinally and transversely stitched open-hole laminate structures. In both cases maximum stress concentration has been found perpendicular at notch to the direction of loading axis, while longitudinally stitched laminate showed 14% higher strength to transversely stitched laminate. This is because longitudinal stitch being able to suppress damage propagation in the direction of failure. Using this finite element technique, FEM result showed a good agreement with the experimental result for open-hole laminates stitched oriented on longitudinal and transverse directions i.e. 7% and 8% error respectively.

1 INTRODUCTION

Light weight and high strength is today's structural demand for next generation aircraft and high performance automobile from economic and environmental point of view. To address these demand aircraft industries have focused on excessive use of advance composite materials on primary and secondary structures, similarly automobile industries have focused on composite monocoque structures. Woven fabric gained attraction because of its lower manufacturing cost and stability along 0° and 90° to unidirectional laminates. Meanwhile, notches and cutouts on structures are inevitable due to various requirements. From design point of view, discontinuities on structure are susceptible to damage initiation [1, 2]. On the other hand, stitching through thickness has improved in-plane characteristics and suppress delamination [3]. Thus stitching pattern on the vicinity of open-hole

laminates is essential for the further development of structure with enhanced strength avoiding catastrophic failure.

At an early stage, Whitney and Nuismer formulated two criterion for open-hole composite laminates, i.e. point stress criterion and average stress criterion [4]. Since then numerous experimental investigations have been carried out for open-hole laminates. X.P Han et al. [5] carried experimental investigation on non-woven composite laminates with circular single and double stitching reinforcement around central hole. K. Gliesche [6] performed optical investigation on open-holed tailored fibre placement process (TFP) reinforced non-woven composite laminates with grating method from GOM corp. Both of these studies agreed with improvement in strength due to reinforcement. Arief et al. [7] experimentally investigated effect of longitudinal and transverse parallel stitch reinforcement on open-hole plain weave woven laminates. It has been concluded with no effect of stitching. However, there is always a contradicting conclusion for the improvement, degradation or neutral on reinforcement around the discontinuity.

It is obvious that woven composite has complex patterns due to its weft and waft tow interlaces. Different numerical formulation, specific programing and commercial finite element tools have been employed to solve the problem[8]. Ishikawa and Chou[9, 10] developed 1D mosaic, fibre undulation and bridging model for the study of thermo-elastic behavior of woven composites. Naik et al. [11] further developed 2D model as an extended undulation model. Cox et al. [12-14] have developed binary model using two node line element and 8-node solid elements representing axial and transverse tows respectively. Jiang WG [15] proposed domain superposition technique by independently meshing tows using solid element. S.D Green[8] modelled 3D satin woven composite unit cell using TexGen pre-processor following voxel method and continuum damage model, which could represent the architecture more realistically. However, it has been considered impractical to model interpenetration at tow crossovers at macroscopic structural level. Focusing on this difficulty, Tong et al. [3] has identified five different modelling strategies.

This paper deals with numerical analysis of open-hole carbon-fibre/epoxy (T300/EP3631) laminates with stitch thread of Kevlar-29 for in-plane behavior on tensile loading. Stitch around the open-hole are oriented on longitudinal and transverse direction having stitch pitch of 3mm and stitch spacing of 12mm. Numerical analysis at macroscopic structural level for the result validation, in-plane characteristics of open-hole stitched laminates have been carried out. This analysis is capable of capturing stress-strain and stress concentration behaviour along the characteristic distance from the discontinuity which was unclear during the experimental analysis.

2. SPECIMEN AND TEST DETAILS

Plain weave woven composite with warp tows (0 degree) and weft tows (90 degree) with stitched had been selected for investigation. Specimen had been prepared with tow width of 1.5mm and thickness 0.2mm from fibre type T300-3K carbon-fibre/epoxy. Through thickness reinforcement had been done by modified locked stitch with linear density 1500 denier Kevlar-29 thread. Stitch had been employed with spacing(s) of 12mm and pitch (p) 3mm. Test laminate consists of twenty ply layers i.e. $[(0/90)]_{20}$. Centrally located hole on laminate had been prepared following ASTM D5766 standard instructions[16]. Specimen of 250 mm x 25mm x 4 mm had been cut from a single mother plate so as to arrange stitch longitudinally and transversely using water-cooled cutting machine, Maruto AC-400CF. Drill bit of diameter 6.30mm had been used for making hole and finished by reamer of diameter 6.35mm. Surface finish had been carried out using abrasive paper 500grit then final finish by 1200 grit.

Instron 8802 with maximum load capacity of 100kN, utilizing dead-load through servo-hydraulic means had been employed for the experimental observation. The loading rate of 1 mm/min had been applied during tensile test without using tabs. However, composite test are often recommended to use friction grip which are finely roughened with serration or cross-cut pattern. These patterns help to transfer and spread load to large possible area, through grip area and minimizing damage of specimen. Wedge grip had been selected for the experiment which has self-tightening mechanism. Moreover, single element strain gauges from Kyowa had been used for strain measurement in conjunction with Kyowa DB-120T8 bridge box for connecting strain gauge, amplification and signal conditioning. Strain gauges type KFG-5-120-C1-23L3M2R with 5mm gauge length and $2.10 \pm 1.0\%$ gauge factor at

operating 24^oC, 50% RH had been arranged on laminate surface by quarter bridge configurations at a distance of 1mm and 5 mm apart from the discontinuity as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic of open-hole laminates with strain gauge arrangement (a) longitudinally stitched (b) transversely stitched

3. ANALYTICAL ANALYSIS

From the theory of macro-mechanics on composites, if the fibre reinforced composite layer is specially orthotropic i.e. layers are at 0 or 90 degrees, balanced and symmetric following condition are satisfied.

$$\begin{aligned} A_{16} &= A_{26} = \alpha_{16} = \alpha_{26} = 0 \\ B_{16} &= B_{26} = \beta_{16} = \beta_{26} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Hence stiffness matrix for the orthotropic plate with in-plane loading N_x, N_y, N_{xy} is represented by;

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \varepsilon_{xy}^0 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{11} & \alpha_{12} & 0 \\ \alpha_{12} & \alpha_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \alpha_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

With the absence of bending loads, all curvatures are zero and strains are constant through thickness. $\varepsilon_x = \varepsilon_x^0, \varepsilon_y = \varepsilon_y^0, \nu_{xy} = \nu_{xy}^0$. Also for homogeneous orthotropic plates under in-plane loading, stress are constant through the thickness giving $\sigma_x = N_x/t, \sigma_y = N_y/t, \sigma_{xy} = N_{xy}/t$. Then, stress-strain relation can be reduced as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_x & -\nu_{xy}/E_x & 0 \\ -\nu_{xy}/E_x & 1/E_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/G_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N_x/t \\ N_y/t \\ N_{xy}/t \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

From (2) and (3)

$$\begin{aligned} E_x &= \frac{1}{t\alpha_{11}} = \frac{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2}{tA_{22}} \\ E_y &= \frac{1}{t\alpha_{22}} = \frac{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2}{tA_{11}} \\ G_{xy} &= \frac{1}{t\alpha_{66}} = \frac{A_{66}}{t} \\ \nu_{xy} &= \frac{\alpha_{12}}{\alpha_{11}} = \frac{A_{12}}{A_{22}} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Now, Stress concentration factor (SCF) with uniaxial in-plane loading in x direction for balanced symmetric orthotropic infinitely wide laminate that satisfies (1) is defined by:

$$k_t^\infty = 1 + \sqrt{\frac{2}{A_{22}} \left[\left(\sqrt{A_{11}A_{22}} \right) - A_{12} + \frac{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2}{2A_{66}} \right]} \quad (5)$$

From (4) and (5), we get

$$k_t^\infty = 1 + \sqrt{2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{E_x}{E_y}} - \nu_{xy} + \frac{E_x}{2G_{xy}} \right)} \quad (6)$$

As theoretical SCF is defined by maximum stress σ_{\max} at discontinuity to nominal stress σ_n computed assuming discontinuity is not present i.e.

$$k_t = \frac{\sigma_{\max}}{\sigma_n} \quad (7)$$

Meanwhile, stress distribution due to open-hole for above condition is approximated by the following expression:

$$\sigma_x \approx \left[1 + \frac{\xi^2}{2} + \frac{3\xi^4}{2} - \frac{(k_t^\infty - 3)}{2} (5\xi^6 - 7\xi^8) \right] f_w \sigma_n \quad (8)$$

Where, $\xi = \frac{a}{y}$, $f_w = \frac{2 + (1 - 2a/w)^3}{3(1 - 2a/w)}$

a = radius of the hole

y = distance from the center of the hole

f_w = correction factor for finite width plate

w = width of finite plate

It has been noted that correction factor provide less than 10% error on exact solution in most cases if $2a/w \leq 1/3$ [17].

Again, effective SCF k_e is given by following expression:

$$k_e = \frac{\sigma_x}{\sigma_n} \approx \left[1 + \frac{\xi^2}{2} + \frac{3\xi^4}{2} - \frac{(k_t^\infty - 3)}{2} (5\xi^6 - 7\xi^8) \right] f_w \quad (9)$$

Normally, k_e is lower than k_t because of reduced sensitivity of the material to notches. The notch sensitivity is defines by:

$$q = \frac{k_e - 1}{k_t - 1} \quad (10)$$

Notch sensitivity ranges from 0 to 1 indicating no sensitivity to notch to full sensitivity to notch, which depends upon notch size, laminate material and laminate layup. Failure of laminate is supposed to occur when the nominal stress of notched laminate reaches the stress of the unnotched laminate. This nominal stress at failure is also called notched strength because it represents the apparent strength of the notched laminate.

3.1. STRESS CALCULATION FROM THE STRAIN

When mechanical properties of woven fabric laminates are assumed to be orthotropic axial stresses around the notch can be calculated from measured strain from stress-strain relation using the following expression.

$$\sigma_x = \frac{E_x \varepsilon_x}{1 - \nu_{xy}^2 \left(\frac{E_y}{E_x} \right)} + \frac{\nu_{xy} E_y \varepsilon_y}{1 - \nu_{xy}^2 \left(\frac{E_y}{E_x} \right)} \quad (11)$$

4. MACROSCOPIC MODELLING FOR STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

Plain weaves stitched composites as explained on section 2 have been considered at macro-scale. Laminates with stitch along longitudinal and transverse direction are modelled with 8-node solid elements for structural-macroscopic analysis. Commercially available finite element analysis (FEA) software: MSC Patran and MSC Nastran have been used for pre/post processing and solver respectively.

Figure 2: (i) Schematic of Plain weave woven composite (ii) Cross-section of Plain Weave woven unit cell (iii) Micro-structures of Plain weave woven composite unit cell (a) Void/Pure Resin (b) Undulated (c) Straight cross ply

It has been considered that during macroscopic modelling, it is not practical to model microscopic details as unit cell modelling shown in figure 2. Thus a single micro-block can be used as an assembling unit for different types of macro-blocks so as to build woven fabric laminates[18]. Straight cross ply micro-block, which represent majority of the structure has been modelled considering woven characteristic. Hence, single solid element through thickness has been used that could represent warp and weft yarn. These elements have been so arranged that its internal orientation are in 0° and 90° thus it can give combine overall effect of woven ply. Along with this, some assumptions have been made to cope with the complexity of architecture, which is highlighted below:

- The plain weave woven fabrics are assumed to be balanced, i.e. woven fabric unit cell, the fiber volume fraction and mechanical properties along the warp direction is exactly the same as those in weft direction.
- The warp and weft tows are packed perfectly and the void of resin and nesting resin on the interlacing areas between warp and weft tows are ignored.
- The macro-structure of woven fabric is orthotropic and homogeneous.
- All lamina undergo same deformation.

Laminate finite element modelling technique imbedded has been customized to model the laminate ply-by-ply, so as to obtain global and localized stress-strain distribution. On the conventional process laminate formulation, different stacking sequences are defined within a single element through thickness. While in this formulation, each lamina in laminates is modelled with single element through thickness. Also lamina properties were assigned separately. While on the other hand, nodes in between two laminas have been shared, making common nodes in between two laminas. Interfaces between matrix and stitch yarns are assumed to be perfectly glued and modeled by contact capability in the solver. Furthermore, node-to-surface algorithm of contact detection has been adopted to represent contact on deformable body.

Figure 3 depicts finite element model of unstitched, transversely and longitudinally stitched open-hole plain weave woven laminates with boundary conditions respectively. Specimen was grip at 50mm on either ends, thus it has been represented by constraining translation on y and z direction and constraining rotation on x, y & z. Tensile forces have been applied at the end of the structure along x direction. Open-hole laminates consists of maximum element number of 115120 and node number of 158562. Material properties for carbon-fiber T300-3K and Kevlar-29 stitch are listed in table 1.

Figure 3: Loading and boundary conditions for open-hole laminates

Material Properties T300-3K		Material Properties Kevlar-29	
Longitudinal Modulus (GPa) E_x	139.18	Longitudinal Modulus (GPa) E_x	70.5
Transverse Modulus (GPa) E_y	9.71	Transverse Modulus (GPa) E_y	2.59
Out-of-plane Modulus (GPa) E_z	9.71	Out-of-plane Modulus (GPa) E_z	2.59
In-plane Shear Modulus (GPa) G_{xy}	5.58	In-plane Shear Modulus (GPa) G_{xy}	2.17
Out-of-plane Shear Modulus (GPa) G_{xz}	5.58	Out-of-plane Shear Modulus (GPa) G_{xz}	2.17
Out-of-plane Shear Modulus (GPa) G_{yz}	3.76	Out-of-plane Shear Modulus (GPa) G_{yz}	2.17
Poisson's ratio ν_{xy}	0.29	Poisson's ratio ν_{xy}	0.36
Poisson's ratio ν_{zx}	0.02	Poisson's ratio ν_{zx}	0.0132
Poisson's ratio ν_{yz}	0.40	Poisson's ratio ν_{yz}	0.36

Table 1: Material Properties

5. DATA AND DISCUSSION

5.1. STRESS-STRAIN BEHAVIOR

Figure 4: Stress-strain distributions for longitudinally stitched open-hole laminate

Figure 5: Stress-strain distributions for transversely stitched open-hole laminate

Experimental validations for stress-strain distribution have been done with finite element analysis. Figure 4 and figure 5 depicts open-hole tension result on longitudinally stitched and transversely stitched laminates at characteristic length (y-a) of 1 mm and 5 mm. This graph shows an error of 5.18% and 4.97% at 1mm characteristic length and error of 6.84% and 7.92% at 5mm characteristic length for open-hole longitudinally stitched and transversely stitched laminates respectively. Using this finite element (FE) technique, it showed a good agreement with the experimental result.

5.2. STRESS CONCENTRATION FACTOR

Analytical analysis for stress concentration behaviour has been evaluated using expression 9 on section 3. FE analysis for open-hole laminates without stitch has been done to correlate with analytical result, which showed a good agreement (figure 6). Analytical and FE result are capable to predict SCF distribution effectively which was not clear during experimental investigation. Moreover, FEA has been able to show the effect of stitching and its effectiveness on orientation around the notch more significantly.

Figure 6 exhibit stress concentration factor for analytical solution and FEA solution for unstitched, transversely stitched and longitudinally stitched laminates. These graphs have been further compared with each other concluding that transversely stitched open-hole laminate has reduced SCF by 8.07% than unstitched laminates. Similarly, longitudinally stitched open-hole laminate has reduced SCF by 14.29% than transversely stitched open-hole laminate and concurrently 21.22% than unstitched open-hole laminate. It is to be noted that these comparison have been done with corresponding node at characteristic length.

Finite element stress concentration result showed that notch has severe effect on both unstitched and stitched laminates. SCF along characteristic length has reduced significantly on longitudinal stitched open-hole laminates than transversely stitched and unstitched open-hole laminates. Stitching has helped to improve notch strength. Unstitched laminates had higher notch sensitivity than transversely stitched laminates and transversely stitched had higher notch sensitivity than longitudinally stitched laminates. This is because longitudinal stitch being able to suppress damage propagation. While transversely stitched laminates showed less significant effect for the suppression of crack propagation than longitudinally stitched. However SCF away from vicinity of notch remains similar. In other words, these graphs have similar slope away from vicinity of notch.

Figure 6: Stress concentration factor distribution for plain weave open-hole laminates

6. CONCLUSION

From the numerical analysis some of the conclusion can be drawn which are highlighted as follows:

- Longitudinally stitched open-hole laminates is more effective than transversely stitched laminates with uniaxial tension loading. Longitudinal stitch help to decrease notch sensitivity and improve notch strength than transverse stitched, similarity holds for transversely stitch to unstitched open-hole laminates.
- SCF has been reduced on through-thickness stitching by 21% and 8% for longitudinal and transverse stitch respectively compared to unstitched open-hole laminates. Reduced SCF indicates the improvement of structural performance.
- Stitch orientation plays a vital role for the suppression of damage on discontinuous structure. Thus it is important to study its behaviour with finite element method to prevent catastrophic failures.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Authors would like to thank Tokyo Metropolitan Government for the financial support from Asian Network of Major Cities 21 (ANMC-21) project.

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